

DEVELOPMENT AND PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF AN ELECTRIC-POWERED ALUMINIUM MELTING FURNACE

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ABSTRACT

Furnaces are used to heat solid materials to change their shape or properties. Melting furnace is mainly used with non-ferrous metals. This research work developed an electric-powered crucible furnace for the purpose of melting Aluminium scraps. It consists of a 2500W electrical element, metallic plates and pipes, insulating materials and an electric centrifugal blower that helps to circulate the air within the furnace. The furnace is capable of melting aluminum scraps in laboratories and workshops. Experimental run was setup to melt different masses of 2mm thickness of Aluminium scraps. The masses melted are: 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 3.5, 4.0 and 5.0 kg. Tests carried out showed that it required about 20.25 minutes heating up the furnace to the required melting temperature of Aluminium (660.5 °C). It also took average of 37.50 minutes to melt 5kg of Aluminium scraps. An efficiency rate of the furnace is estimated to be about 35.25%.

Keywords: Furnace, Aluminium, Scrap, metal, Heat.

INTRODUCTION

A furnace is essentially a thermal enclosure and is employed to process raw materials at high temperatures both in solid and liquid states. Several industries like iron and steel making, non-ferrous metals production, glass making, manufacturing, ceramic processing, calcinations in cement production, employ the use of furnace (Ekpe *et al.*, 2015; Adeolu *et al.* 2017). Furnace converts chemical energy of a fuel or electrical energy into heat. The heat is then used to raise the temperature of the crucible or stock placed within the furnace for melting or smelting. Oven furnaces are operated at a low temperature depending on their types or purpose but high temperature furnaces are mostly used in foundry industries and others such as extraction of metal from ore. Chemical plants and oil refineries equally employed high temperature furnace for fractional distillation likewise in the industries and laboratories for making steel and heat treatments of materials for the purpose of changing their molecular structures (Bala 2005; Abed,

2013). Previous studies show the importance of efficient and effective furnace in the production process involved in foundry technology hence the local foundry craftsman and technicians use furnace for casting different objects such as machine parts, domestic cooking pots, spoons, frying pans etc. According to Katerina *et al.* (2016) they concluded that for a nation to advance technologically, it must be able to harness and convert its mineral resources, fabricate most of its equipment and machines locally. Abed *et al.* (2013) also emphasized the importance of melting and heat treatment of metals in manufacturing process. Ability to harness, convert the mineral resources into what is beneficial to the people of the country and the world at large, development of machine and equipment locally are some of the attributes of technologically advanced countries. According to Ahmed (2009); the production of metal is one of the major industrial practices that should be in the forefront of industrialization because metals are versatile elements whose field of application are very wide in human lives and development of a country. Statistics have shown that furnaces are one of the largest consumers of energy and are facing increased pressure to produce high quality products at equal or lower cost to be competitive (Oyawale, 2011; Kulani *et al.*, 2018). The main reason why oil fired furnace is commonly used is that they are not expensive, easy to operate, melting of small batches of different alloys which are melt directly in the furnace and the maintenance ability very economical friendly (Adeolu *et al.*, 2017; Kulla *et al.*, 2005). Various literatures reviewed on existing standard mini-electric furnaces for melting Aluminium showed that they can attain a temperature of well over 1000°C within an hour Ahmed (2009); Abed (2013); Adeolu (2017) however, the present work examines the performance of a locally fabricated Aluminium melting furnace.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Procurement of Aluminium scraps used for this research work took place at Lagos, Nigeria. The criteria for the various components of the furnace are based on local availability, function ability, durability, environmental and operating conditions. The basic components of the furnace are: an electrical element rated 2500 watt, metallic plates and pipes, insulating materials and an electric centrifugal blower that

helps to circulate the air within the furnace. The body is formed from a cylindrical shaped of 2mm mild steel sheet. The body forms a melting chamber enclosing the insulating materials, refractory blocks and crucible. The crucible is cylindrical in shape and made of a locally made ceramic pot placed in the melting chamber for the purpose of holding the molten Aluminium. The furnace cover is constructed with the same material used for the body.

Table 1: Design parameters of the furnace

Parameter	Values
<i>Furnace capacity</i>	<i>0.442m³</i>
<i>Heat Input</i>	<i>812.5KJ</i>
<i>Heat Output</i>	<i>286.33KJ</i>
<i>Initial temperature</i>	<i>20°C</i>
<i>Final temperature</i>	<i>725°C</i>
<i>Efficiency</i>	<i>35.25%</i>
<i>Heat loss</i>	<i>526.18KJ</i>
<i>Mean mass of Aluminium produced</i>	<i>2.82kg</i>
<i>Specific heat capacity of Aluminium</i>	<i>900J/kg°C</i>
<i>Mean maximum temperature of the furnace</i>	<i>689.13°C</i>

Design analysis

1. Furnace Capacity

The volume of the crucible is calculated in line with the method used by [2] and evaluated with the aid of equation (1).

$$V = \pi R^2 H = 54418437.5 \text{mm}^3 = 4418.4375 \text{m}^3 \quad (1)$$

where, V, R and H are the volume (mm³), radius (75mm) and height (250mm) of the cylindrical crucible specifications.

2. Heat input to the furnace chamber through the electrical element. This is estimated in equation (2)

$$Q_a = 10 \times 250 = 2500W \quad (2)$$

where Q_a , I , V are heat input (watts), current (10A) and voltage (250V).

3. Heat output

The heat output is calculated using equation (3)

$$Q_b = 5 \times M \times 3c_p \times 3\Delta T = 53172.5KJ \quad 5881.25W \quad (3)$$

where Q_b , M , C_p and ΔT are quantity of heat, mass of Aluminium melted (5kg), specific heat capacity of Aluminium (900J/Kg°C) and change in temperature of the Aluminium from the its initial temperature before entering the furnace and its final temperature (705°C).

4. Heat loss

The heat loss is the difference between the heat input and the heat output. It is computed as in equation (4)

$$Q_l = 5 [Q_a - Q_b] = 51618.75W \quad (4)$$

where Q_l = [Heat loss]

Q_a = (2500W [Heat input] and

Q_b = (881.25W [Heat output]

5. Efficiency

The efficiency of the furnace is estimated in line with [2] and evaluated in equation (5)

$$\eta = 5 \frac{Q_a}{Q_b} = 35.25\% \quad (5)$$

Where η = Efficiency

Q_a and Q_b are heats input (2500W and output (881.25W).

Performance Evaluation of the Furnace

The developed furnace was evaluated by melting 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5 and 3.0 kg of Aluminium scraps respectively. The experimental setup is as shown in figure 1. The furnace was fired and the time taken to raise the temperature to 800 °C

Table 2 also depicts the results obtained during the experimental runs.

Figure 1: Experimental setup

Table 2: Result obtained during experimental runs

Experim ental runs	Mass of Aluminium scraps	Time taken to raise the furnace temperature to 660°C (min)	Holding time (min)	Total melting time (min)	Temperature of the melting furnace (°C)
1	1.00	20.00	3.50	23.50	685
2	1.50	19.50	5.00	24.50	697
3	2.00	20.00	6.00	26.00	710
4	2.50	21.00	8.00	29.00	725
5	3.00	20.00	10.00	30.50	736
6	3.50	20.50	14.00	34.50	750
7	4.00	20.00	16.50	36.50	762
8	5.00	21.00	17.50	37.50	787
Mean	2.82	20.25	80.50	30.25	731.50

Melting rate is evaluated in line with the method used by [6] and computed as in equation (6).

$$\text{Melting rate} = 5 \frac{\text{Total mass of aluminium scraps charge (kg)}}{\text{Total time taken to melt scraps charge (seconds)}} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Melting Rate} &= 5 \frac{5.62}{30.25} \\ &= 0.93 \text{ kg/min.} \end{aligned}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Aluminium melting furnace developed is done with the designed parameters highlighted in table 2. The major specifications of the furnace are mean capacity of melting pot: 2.82 kg (max), mean operating temperature: 731.50°C, operating voltage: 250V, power consumption: 2500W. From the results obtained above, the efficiency of the furnace was calculated to be 35.25% and melting rate of 0.93 kg/min. This is in conformity with the research works of Ahmed (2009); Abed (2013); Adeolu (2017) who emphasized the importance of melting and heat treatment of metals in manufacturing process; other conventional furnaces developed by other researchers in the field of foundry technology follows the same principle.

CONCLUSION

This study developed an electric-powered Aluminium melting furnace with the capacity to melt 2. 82 kg mean mass of Aluminium scraps at a maximum mean temperature of 689. 13°C within 316 seconds mean time.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We wish to acknowledge the intellectual contributions of Engr. Dr. O. O. Awolola of the Department of Mechatronics Engineering, The Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro, Ogun State while appreciating the technical contributions of Messr. Lawal, A.G and Mr. T.D. Musa in the Foundry Workshop of the Department of Mechanical Engineering, the Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro.

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